

«بِسْمِ اللّٰهِ الرَّحْمٰنِ الرَّحِیْمِ»

موضوع ارئه: COPII

(coat protein complex II)

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The Sar1 GTPase

(A) In the cytosolic GDP-bound state (D), the amphipathic helix of Sar1 is retracted in a hydrophobic pocket. Upon nucleotide exchange on the ER membrane, GTP binding (T) induces a conformational change that expels the helix, anchoring Sar1 on the membrane until GTP is hydrolyzed.

(B) Membrane-bound Sar1 is capable of inducing membrane curvature. Athin section electron micrograph showing the deformation of spherical liposomes into narrow tubules after incubation with Sar1 and GTP. Scale bar = 100 nm. Reprinted from with permission from Elsevier.

(C) A helical wheel plot of the first 18 amino acids of the Sar1 amphipathic helix reveals a broad hydrophobic face (dark green) that becomes buried in the membrane (yellow), whereas the polar face (positively charged residues in blue, negatively charged in red, hydroxylated in purple) may be partially exposed to the cytosol.

Structure and domain arrangement of the Sec23/Sec24 complex. Ribbon diagram of the Sec23/Sec24/Sar1 crystal structure. Sar1 is colored red and Sec23 and Sec24 are colored according to their domain structures as indicated. The blue line represents the lipid bilayer that would conform to the curvature of the inner, concave face of the Sec23/Sec24 complex. The three known cargo-binding sites on Sec24 are indicated as the A-, B- and C-sites.

Three views of the Sec13/Sec31 cage. Single-particle reconstruction of an assembled Sec13/Sec31 cage reveals a cuboctahedral structure. As most easily seen in the first panel, each vertex is generated by the convergence of four elongated edges, each likely composed of a Sec13/Sec31 heterotetramer. The cage diameter of ~60 nm conforms to the approximate size of a COPII vesicle (scale bar = 500Å°).

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COPII-mediated vesicle formation at a glance

Relative size of COPII vesicles

Structural model of COPII outer cage assembly

COPII component paralogs and disease

Yeast COPII	Mammalian COPII	Associated diseases
Sar1p	Sar1A Sar1B	Chylomicron retention disease, Anderson disease
Sec23p	Sec23A Sec23B	Cranio-lenticulo-sutural dysplasia Congenital dyserythropoietic anemia type II
Sec24p (Iss1)* (Lst1)*	Sec24A Sec24B Sec24C Sec24D	Craniorachischisis and other planar cell polarity phenotypes
Sec13p	Sec13	
Sec31p	Sec31A Sec31B	

*Yeast homologs of Sec24p

ER exit sites

Members of both the inner (Sec24B) and outer (Sec31A) COPII coat are found concentrated at punctae on the ER membrane called ER exit sites.

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